

ELIXIR Commissioned Service

ELIXIR Data Platform

Connecting and brokering Node contributions to ELIXIR Data resources
(WP2)

D2.1 Description of landscape analysis including collection of user and repository requirements

Tier: Technology

Priority Area: Data Platform ([2024-TECHNOLOGY-Data](#))

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents a comprehensive analysis of data brokering and submission practices within life sciences, focusing on ELIXIR and related repositories. The study addresses challenges arising from inconsistent terminology, fragmented workflows, and limited support for multi-omics data deposition. Data brokering—defined as the mediation or facilitation of data submission on behalf of researchers—can take multiple forms, including direct submission by technical specialists, consultancy support, and provision of brokering tools. Survey results from 38 European professionals highlight the prevalence of intermediary roles, with 60% submitting data on behalf of original authors.

Our landscape analysis examined 13 key repositories, assessing their capabilities to support brokered submissions, multi-omics data, and cross-repository data linkage. Findings reveal that while repositories commonly distinguish submitter and author roles, broker roles are poorly recognized, and tool usage is rarely tracked. Multi-omics submission remains fragmented, with only a limited set of resources providing explicit guidance. Current linking approaches rely heavily on manual cross-referencing using accession numbers, publication IDs, or BioSample identifiers.

Case studies—such as ArrayExpress to ENA, EVA, MGnify, and ProteomeXchange—illustrate existing brokering workflows and highlight benefits (e.g., streamlined submission, reduced duplication) and limitations (e.g., differing policies, technical constraints). These analyses underpin recommendations to standardize role definitions, enhance tool traceability, and harmonize multi-omics submissions across repositories. Implementing these measures will

reduce researcher burden, improve interoperability, and support FAIR-aligned data sharing, ultimately facilitating more efficient and reproducible life sciences research.

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

DDBJ	DNA Data Bank of Japan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
ELIXIR	European Life-sciences Infrastructure for biological Information
ENA	European Nucleotide Archive
EVA	European Variation Archive
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
INSDC	International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration
NCBI	National Center for Biotechnology Information
PX	ProteomeXchange (PX) consortium
RDM	Research Data Management

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Introduction

Tim Berners-Lee, a leading authority in the world of data and analytics, once said “Data is a precious thing and will last longer than the systems themselves.” At a time when the scientific community is generating data at an unprecedented pace and quantity, whether from experiments, modelling or biocuration, it is essential that these be open and FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable). It is no longer acceptable to publish results without providing the data on which the results are based, and journals are increasingly requiring that authors deposit the data (and their corresponding metadata) in a publicly accessible repository. In this context, the ELIXIR Data Platform WP2¹ provides an essential forum to connect data resources with data producers across various ELIXIR nodes, to maximise the use, re-use and value of their data.

While a submitter may be one of the persons who generated the data or an author who wrote the manuscript about the data, it may also be a third party, generally referred to as a broker. Given the crucial role that brokers can play, it is important to examine the different ways in which they facilitate data transfer, aggregation and discovery, on a data producer's behalf. To begin with, different types of brokering will be defined in WP2. This will be followed by a description of the landscape of the current best practices and capability to receive data via a broker or a brokerage platform for selected repositories, with a focus on ELIXIR Nodes. In a later stage of the project plan (i.e., Activity 2), this information will be summarized and formalized in ELIXIR research data management (RDM) resources such as RDMkit² and FAIRsharing Collections³.

Scientific research is increasingly adopting a holistic, systems-level approach to gain a more comprehensive understanding of biological processes and diseases. Multi-omics exemplifies this shift, enabling analysis of data from multiple "omics" domains (e.g. genomics, proteomics, transcriptomics) and leading to better understanding of complex inter-relationships between biological processes. In this context, data are often deposited in multiple repositories, making it essential to preserve links between them to support effective discovery. Hence this report also examines the current capacity of repositories to support linking of datasets as part of a multi-omics submission.

¹ <https://elixir-europe.org/platforms/data>

² <https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/>

³ <https://fairsharing.org/>

Methodology

Definitions of Data Brokering

The concept of a data broker generally refers to an entity that collects, processes, enriches, and sells or licenses data to third parties. The term “brokering” has been applied in varied and sometimes inconsistent ways within the life sciences data management community, creating a need for conceptual clarity. To inform the definitions used in this study, we examined selected earlier and current uses of the term. The earliest instance identified was in the EMBL-EBI Annual Scientific Report 2011⁴, where “data-brokering” referred to a metadata submission scheme from ENA to ArrayExpress and to BioSamples. Indeed, the term is also used to describe cases in which data submission occurs across multiple repositories without direct involvement from the authors or scientific contributors.

We then reviewed its use in the ELIXIR-CONVERGE project documentation⁵, where brokering is framed as the coordinated submission of research data to appropriate repositories via tools such as COPO⁶ and FAIRDOME-SEEK⁷. Similarly, the term “broker” can also refer to a tool or piece of software that facilitates (meta)data mediation or exchange, as described in the publication “Introducing an Enhanced Metadata Broker for Manufacturing Data Spaces”⁸.

Finally, we consulted the Data Brokering guidance in the ELIXIR Research Data Management Kit (RDMkit)⁹, which describes brokering as a role undertaken by a person supporting researchers in their data submission, and characterises it as less technical and not only software-based. In addition, the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA), one of the ELIXIR Core Data Resources, supports the brokering concept specifically at the level of submission tasks, by enabling data to be submitted via a broker account that is distinct from standard user accounts¹⁰. Insights from these sources guided our analysis of current usage and the development of the working definitions adopted in this study, which are discussed in greater detail in the results section.

⁴ https://www.embl.org/documents/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/ebi_ar_2011.pdf

⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7503649>

⁶ <https://copo-project.org/>

⁷ <https://fairdomseek.org/>

⁸ <https://doi.org/10.1145/3685651.3686699>

⁹ https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/data_brokering

¹⁰ <https://academic.oup.com/nar/article/53/D1/D49/7903379>

Survey of Data Submission and Brokering Support Activities

We first created a 'Data Submission Survey'¹¹ with the objective of defining the various roles and related tasks in data deposition processes. An additional purpose was to agree on standardized definitions for different types of brokering, and to establish a point of contact for further inquiries, both for deposition to repositories and for interactions between repositories. The survey was targeted at anyone working in the life sciences domain to capture as broad a scope as possible, and was circulated amongst WP2 member networks for 3 weeks.

38 people responded to the survey, with 60% of those submitting data on behalf of original data owners.

Through the survey we also identified a list of repositories to take forward through the rest of WP2. We selected the top 13 most submitted to data deposition repositories, including both ELIXIR Core Data Resources (CDR's) and some others (Table 1).

Table 1. Data deposition repositories which are the subject of this report.

Repository	URL
ArrayExpress*	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biostudies/arrayexpress
BioImage Archive	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/bioimage-archive
BioSamples	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biosamples
BioStudies	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biostudies
EGA	https://ega-archive.org
EMDB	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/emdb
EMPIAR	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/empiar
ENA	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena
FEGA Sweden**	https://fega.nbis.se/
MetaboLights	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metabolights
PDBe	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/pdbe

¹¹<https://forms.gle/Z9DDwTEHs5D6aj7R6>

PRIDE	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/pride
Zenodo	https://zenodo.org

* ArrayExpress is a collection within BioStudies¹²

** While still connected to the EGA network, the FEGA Sweden node hosts and manages data locally, so it is referred to as a separate repository¹³

Landscape Analysis of Repositories: Capabilities for Data Submission, Brokering, Multi-Omics and Data Linkage

Having identified the list of repositories to take forward in this WP, we then conducted a high-level landscape analysis of their capacity to support the key capabilities below:

- receiving data via a broker/brokering platform (based on typical broker tasks identified from the survey)
- submission of multi-omics data
- linking of multi-omics data across multiple repositories

where linking of siloed datasets is a crucial technical requirement for multi-omics data deposition.

Each capability was further broken down into specific themes, which are detailed here¹⁴. Please note that any boxes in red indicate information that has not been captured. This is a working document that we will continue elaborating as part of our work on the next WP activity.

The landscape analysis was conducted using publicly available documentation and consultations with dedicated repository contacts. Further information on this will be presented in the results section.

Although potential recommendations for improvement can already be inferred from this report, they will be further developed in Activity 2 in collaboration with the ELIXIR RDM Community.

¹² Sarkans et al. (2021). From ArrayExpress to BioStudies. *Nucleic acids research*, 49(D1), D1502–D1506. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkaa1062>

¹³ D'Altri et al. The Federated European Genome–Phenome Archive as a global network for sharing human genomics data. *Nat Genet* 57, 481–485 (2025).

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41588-025-02101-9>

¹⁴<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1OKPkoBJxA7wTIALmj8wviarfZdX-YWyQAURz-mOf61o/edit?usp=sharing>

Results

Data Submission: Roles, Relationships, and Workflows

The landscape of data brokering and data submission is often marked by confusion and inconsistency, largely due to varying interpretations of roles, responsibilities, and processes. Perspectives differ across stakeholders—for example, between data producers and data repositories, or even among repositories themselves. These differences can lead to miscommunication and fragmented practices. To begin addressing this challenge and work toward greater clarity and harmonization, we start by presenting a set of definitions that frame data brokering and submission as interconnected yet distinct components of the research data lifecycle.

Data submission

It is commonly understood in the life sciences that data submission refers to the formal process of depositing research datasets—such as sequencing results or images—into public or institutional repositories for storage, access, or review. Data submission therefore refers to the process of uploading data and metadata to a designated repository, system, or authority for storage, processing, or dissemination.

Data submitter

According to the Contributor Role Ontology, the “submitter role”¹⁵ *is realized through the act of formally submitting or depositing an artifact to be included in some larger resource (e.g. database, registry, collection, etc.)*. Other life sciences ontologies also provide definitions for this concept:

- Experimental Factor Ontology (EFO) - “submitter”¹⁶: A person who presents or submits something (e.g., a proposal or protocol) for formal consideration or review by others.
- Ontology for Biomedical Investigations (OBI) - “reporting party role”¹⁷: a study personnel role played by a party who reports the outcome of a study component.

While the term “data submitter” conceptually refers to the agent responsible for initiating and authorizing the submission of data, its practical implementation within repositories is often tightly linked to a specific user **account**—typically identified by an email address—through which the deposition is carried out. This involves completing the technical steps on the repository’s website, such as **uploading** raw data files and metadata. Responsibilities of data submitter include:

¹⁵ http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/CRO_0000105

¹⁶ http://www.ebi.ac.uk/efo/EFO_0001741

¹⁷ http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/OBI_0000068

- Ensuring they have authority to submit the data.
- Specifying the status of the submission or maintaining the release date of data.
- Maintaining data and metadata records.

Author

An author is someone who has contributed significantly to the conception, design, execution, or interpretation of a research study and is credited in related publications, datasets or other research outputs. Examples of ontologies terms for “author” as role are the “authorship role” term¹⁸ from the SCoRO ontology and the “author” term¹⁹ from schema.org.

The roles of author and data submitter can overlap but are not necessarily synonymous. While authors often submit their own data, there are instances where data submission is handled by someone else, such as a data manager, a data steward, or in general a more technical expert. In such cases, the data submitter may not be listed as an author on the datasets or related manuscripts.

Relation between author and data submitter

If the author and data submitter are not the same person, the author authorizes a designated data submitter to manage the submission of research data to repositories. The data submitter acts as the intermediary between the author or organization and the data repository, facilitating communication and ensuring the proper handling of data. However, the data submitter operates solely under the guidance and instructions of the author or the organization, ensuring that all actions align with the research objectives, ethical standards, and institutional policies.

While the roles of submitter and author regarding deposition in repositories are relatively clear, the definition of brokering roles and tasks varies depending on the data submission workflow. To address this, we first introduce the two main data flows characterised in this report and then provide definitions of “broker” and “brokering” roles for each.

Data submission workflow: two key categories

For the purposes of this report, we distinguish between two main categories of data submission workflows (Figure 1):

1. From data producers to repositories

This category involves researchers or research groups (data producers) depositing datasets into public repositories directly or with the support of RDM professionals.

¹⁸ <http://purl.org/spar/scoro/AuthorshipRole>

¹⁹ <https://schema.org/author>

2. Between data deposition databases

Data submission between repositories refers to the transfer, harvesting, or synchronization of datasets and metadata from one repository to another, without direct involvement from the authors or submitter, to enable aggregation, preservation, or wider visibility.

Figure 1. Data submission workflows. In workflow 1, one of the data producers (author) or a data broker (RDM professional) acts on behalf of the authors to submit the data to a data repository. In this case, the data submission takes place between the data producers (or a broker acting in their name) and the data repository. In workflow 2, a data repository submits data to another data repository - in this case, the data submission takes place between data repositories.

From data producers to repositories

Survey respondent profile and data submission practices

In order to characterize the support roles involved in data submission to public repositories, we asked professionals across Europe about the types of assistance they typically offer. A total of 38 professionals responded to the survey, representing a diverse group of institutions across Europe: 12 from EBI resources, 6 from the SIB Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics, and 20 from various other organizations. Among these respondents, approximately 60% reported that they submit data on behalf of the original data owners, highlighting the active role these

professionals play as intermediaries or data brokers in facilitating data deposition to public repositories.

The multifaceted role of data brokering

Across European institutions, support for these workflows encompasses a broad spectrum of activities. Professionals engaged in facilitating data submission provide both technical services—such as software development, automation, and data transformation—and non-technical support, including repository selection advice, licensing guidance, documentation, training, and user assistance. From the survey responses, we identified three main categories of support activities related to data submission or brokering from data producers to public repositories.

Broker: when the data submitter is not among the authors

In this category the data submitter is not one of the dataset's authors or scientific contributors, but typically a technical specialist or RDM professional. These individuals perform the submission on behalf of the authors and provide essential support by:

- Using their own institutional or personal accounts to submit the data;
- Acting on behalf of the original authors, handling submission logistics and repository communications;
- Performing technical tasks such as metadata registration and data files transfer;
- Mediating communication between the data producers and repository staff to ensure accuracy, compliance, and timely resolution of issues.

Consultant: authors submit, but receive guidance on repository requirements

In this category, the support professional—typically an expert in RDM—does not perform the data submission themselves, but instead provides detailed consultancy and hands-on assistance to help the authors carry out the process. While the authors retain ownership of the submission, using their own accounts, the broker plays a key role in preparing the submission for success. Typical support activities in this category include:

- Advising on what datasets to publish and which repositories are appropriate for a given project or data type;
- Providing hands-on help with metadata, including the use of templates, validation, file formats and ensuring compliance with repository requirements;
- Assisting with file encryption and secure data transfer methods when sensitive data are involved;
- Supporting the preparation of data transfer agreements and choosing a licence when required.
- Metadata curation and releases preparation of the data for submission.

Developer: developers provide software or tools to simplify submissions

In this category, professionals contribute by designing, developing, or maintaining software tools that facilitate the data submission process. These tools are used either by the original data authors or by brokers (of data or information), depending on the institutional setup.

Key activities include:

- Developing submission platforms, scripts, or interfaces that streamline metadata entry, file validation, and data transfer;
- Creating automated workflows to support batch submissions or integration with institutional data systems;
- Ensuring tools are user-friendly and well-documented, enabling researchers and support staff to use them with minimal friction;
- Providing technical support and maintenance to keep brokering tools up to date with repository requirements.

Examples of such tools for domain specific repositories are the ENA Data Submission Toolbox²⁰ and related useGalaxy tools and workflow²¹, COPO²², ISA tools²³, DataPLANT²⁴, FAIRDOM-SEEK²⁵.

Some tools help mainly with metadata preparation, while others also support the transfer of data files to repositories. Many tools are specific to a single repository (e.g., the ENA data submission toolbox) or provide metadata checklists for only one or a few repositories. For multimodal experiments submitted to EMBL-EBI resources, several separate submissions are often needed. At present, there is no single tool for a unified multimodal submission.

How Data Deposition Databases support the brokering roles

We examined the roles recognised and supported by deposition databases in relation to data submission and brokering activities (Table 2). Although the roles of data submitter and author were consistently present, the terminology used to describe them varied. With a few exceptions where controlled vocabularies or ontologies were applied, roles were generally recorded as free text provided by the submitter, with only some indexed or mapped to controlled terms. In addition, repositories did not clearly distinguish between submitter and broker roles (e.g., submitters acting on behalf of authors, the consultants mediating

²⁰ <https://rdm.elixir-belgium.org/ena-submission>

²¹ <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btab421>

²² <https://copo-project.org/about/>

²³ <https://isa-tools.org>

²⁴ <https://doi.org/10.1111/tpj.16474>

²⁵ <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkw1032>

requirements, or developers/providers of brokering tools), and in most cases a single helpdesk contact supported all these functions.

ArrayExpress

Although data submission to ArrayExpress²⁶ starts via the Annotare submission tool, once the entry is fully curated, the experiment will be loaded into the ArrayExpress collection in the BioStudies database.

Data submitter.

Annotare submitter: account holder registering an entry in the Annotare submission tool, providing other contact names for the submission. Annotare submitter can assign the submitter role to a different contact.

BioStudies submitter: An Annotare submission triggers the creation of a BioStudies submitter account, which is assigned to the first contact listed by the Annotare submitter explicitly labeled with the "submitter" role. Used for managing post-submission updates, notifications and correspondence.

Authors. No - more specific roles are offered as a part of the submission process.

Other roles. A controlled vocabulary: array manufacturer, biomaterial provider, biosequence provider, consortium member, consultant, curator, data analyst, data coder, experiment performer, funder, hardware manufacturer, institution, investigator, material supplier role, peer review quality control role, software manufacturer.

BioImage Archive

Uses the same data submission tools as BioStudies, therefore also shares the same concepts for the dataset-people relationship (see below).

BioSamples

Data submitter. *Webin submission account.* ENA Webin authentication for access and authorization is used.

BioStudies

Data submitter. The single registered account through which the deposition is carried out. The data submitter owns the entry submitted to BioStudies. The submitter self-certifies that they have the rights to submit such data to a public archive. The owner can ask BioStudies helpdesk to transfer ownership, or add editing rights for other accounts.

²⁶ A long-standing ELIXIR Core Data Resource, though now discontinued as a stand-alone resource and exists as a data collection in BioStudies (10.1093/nar/gkaa1062).

Authors. Authors, their affiliation and roles are specified in the submission metadata.

Other roles. Can be added in the Contact metadata fields.

EGA

Data submitter. A submitter role is assigned to an EGA registered user account upon request.

Authors. None.

Other roles. For metadata submission, *Collaborators* can be added. Only registered EGA users can be added as collaborators and a permission level must be defined (read-only or read/write).

EMDB

Data submitter. In the Electron Microscopy Data Bank (EMDB), the *depositor* is associated with a specific EMDB submission made through the wwPDB OneDep system and has permission to modify the deposition. The depositor may or may not be the PI. It is the responsibility of the depositor to act on behalf of the PI(s), provide all information accurately and provide a verifiable ORCID or email address to the OneDep system to initiate deposition. There is only one depositor for any given deposition. The *depositor* can grant view, view/edit, view/edit/submit privileges to other accounts, as well as transfer the submission ownership.

Authors. *Contact authors* are responsible for correspondence with wwPDB regarding the EMDB entry. All PIs are automatically also entry contact authors. Anyone listed as a contact author in the entry is informed about deposition, modifications, status changes, release, obsoleting and withdrawal.

Other roles.

Principal Investigator(s) (PI): ultimately, it is the PI(s) who is responsible for the EMDB entry made through the OneDep system. The PI(s) can delegate their responsibilities to a contact author.

Entry author(s): entry authors are associated with an EMDB entry as assigned by the PI(s) and listed by the depositor during submission. Entry-author details must include last name and initials, although a structural genomics centre can be listed as an entry author.

Citation authors: citation authors are authors of the primary publication associated with an EMDB entry.

EMPIAR

Data submitter. The EMPIAR deposition system is user-based. Individual users sign on to the system, and can create and handle multiple depositions. There is only one *depositor* for any given deposition. The depositor can grant view, view/edit, view/edit/submit privileges to other accounts, as well as transfer the submission ownership.

Authors. The names and ORCIDs of all authors associated with the EMPIAR entry are collected and made public upon release. The corresponding author of the paper must be one of the authors associated with the deposition, but does not necessarily have to be the owner of the deposition.

Other roles.

Principal Investigator(s) (PI): The PI(s) scientifically responsible for the study is designated as the owner of the deposition. The owner can delegate the upload and entry of data and metadata to another person. All communication regarding a deposition from the EMPIAR annotation team will be addressed to the owner(s) and the depositor. It is the owner's responsibility to make sure that information is then further channelled to the appropriate authors.

ENA

Data submitter.

Webin submission account: A Webin submission account linked to at least one contact (with a personal email address) is required for data submission to ENA. Each Webin account is permanently associated with a specific group and centre, and all submissions from that account are irrevocably linked to that group and centre.

Broker account: To act as a data submitter on behalf of the author, you must apply for brokering permissions to be added to your ENA account. Using a broker account enables the data submitter to add the name of the institution or organisation as "Broker name".

Authors. The list of account contacts, together with the account owner, is defined as the 'authors' for assemblies. For broker accounts submitting assemblies, the author list must be provided within the manifest files or JSON document. If no author list is provided, it is automatically retrieved from the Webin account.

Other roles. Contacts are other individuals who will have access to the submitter account.

MetaboLights

Data submitter. In MetaboLights, the account responsible for creating a submission is referred to as the *contact*, typically an author or a submitter. This user must be a registered MetaboLights account holder, and their information is stored in the MetaboLights database.

Contact generally serves as the main point of communication. Additional submitters can be granted access by the original submitting account.

Authors. The author list, named *contributors*, includes individuals listed as authors of the publication and is particularly useful when the publication does not have a DOI. These individuals do not automatically receive access to the submission, but could be added as additional data submitters upon request.

Other roles. A broader list of contributors is captured under *People*, which includes individuals involved in the study and is structured according to the ISA framework.

PDB

The same policies and deposition systems are used as for EMDB.

PRIDE

Data submitter. In PRIDE, the account through which data submission occurs is defined as the *data submitter*.

Authors. During submission, the submitter specifies the Principal Investigator (PI) or lab head name in the form. A separate account for the PI can be requested to provide access.

Other roles. Both the submitter and any additional *contacts* (such as a PI account) are listed under general contact information in a PRIDE entry.

Zenodo

Zenodo is a generalist data repository but widely used in EU-funded projects and for research outputs that do not fit into the data type specific deposition databases. It supports community curated collections (examples: ELIXIR, RDA, ...), can issue DOIs and is indexed by Datacite.

Data submitter. The Zenodo deposition system is user-based. Individual users sign on to the system, and can create and handle multiple depositions. There is only one depositor for any given deposition. The depositor can grant view or view/edit privileges to other accounts.

Authors. During submission, the submitter must specify the authors/creators, their affiliation and ORCID in the form (the search for authors is powered by the `_ORCID` datasets). These individuals do not automatically receive access to the submission, but can be granted view or view/edit privileges.

Other roles. Contributors can be specified to provide information about persons or organisations that have contributed to the record. The contributor role is defined using DataCite's "Contributor" vocabulary. The Distributor role "Other" is used for someone

providing administrative services to the author (such as the data broker depositing the data on behalf of the authors in an online repository).

Table 2. Overview of roles in data submission across ELIXIR Deposition Databases (EDDs) and generic repositories (non-EDD).

EDDs	Roles		
	<i>Data submitter</i>	<i>Authors</i>	<i>Other roles</i>
ArrayExpress	Annotare submitter, BioStudies submitter	Contacts	Contacts
BioImageArchive	Submitter	Authors	none
BioSamples	ENA Webin account	none	none
BioStudies	Submitter	Authors	none
EGA	Submitter	none	Collaborators
EMBD	Depositor	Contact authors	PIs, Entry authors, Citation authors
EMPIAR	Depositor	Contact authors	PIs, Entry authors, Citation authors
ENA	Webin account, Broker account & name	Contacts /Authors	none
MetaboLights	Contacts	Contributors	People
PDB	Depositor	Contact authors	PIs, Entry authors, Citation authors
PRIDE	Submitters	Contacts (PI or lab head)	Contacts
Non EDDs			
Zenodo	Submitter	Authors	Contributors

Support for data submission via brokering tool

Several third-party platforms and tools, such as the ENA Data Submission Toolbox²⁷, COPO²⁸, ISA tools²⁹, DataPLANT³⁰, and FAIRDOME-SEEK³¹, have been developed to facilitate data submission, often providing alternative graphical or command-line interfaces for submitting

²⁷ <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btab421>

²⁸ <https://copo-project.org/about/>

²⁹ <https://isa-tools.org>

³⁰ <https://doi.org/10.1111/tpj.16474>

³¹ <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkw1032>

to one or more repositories. However, deposition databases generally provide limited support for systematically recording or tracking which tool or platform was used for submission, and such information is often poorly documented. In the case of the ENA Data Submission Toolbox, the tool developer implemented a metadata field, indexed by ENA, to capture the name of the submission tool used. This enables the identification and retrieval of datasets submitted via the ENA Data Submission Toolbox in ENA.

Between data deposition databases

The growing complexity of high throughput biology assays means that occasionally parts of (meta)data submitted to one database better fit in another one to enable aggregation, efficient preservation, or wider visibility.

However, defining and standardising the data submission workflow between deposition databases is inherently complex, as it involves different types and levels of information that may be shared, transferred, or harvested across systems. This complexity is further compounded by the variety of ways in which (meta)data management is implemented at the technical level within each database and supporting infrastructure. For instance, it is often difficult to determine what should be categorised as brokering as opposed to metadata harvesting or data sharing, since some underlying processes might overlap in practice. Exchanges between repositories might involve metadata, data files, or both. As a result, establishing consistent categories for these workflows is challenging, as practices and technical solutions vary considerably across repositories.

Below we describe a set of known scenarios in which such exchanges occur between repositories.

From ArrayExpress to ENA

The first assays to measure gene expression were microarray-based. ArrayExpress database was developed and launched in 2002, together with community guidelines for good practices of sharing experimental metadata, and the associated data formats. The term “FAIR” did not exist at the time, but this work was essentially following the FAIR principles for gene expression data. As sequencing-based technologies developed and started to replace array-based assays, the ArrayExpress processes and infrastructure was adjusted accordingly. It was clear that splitting the responsibility of data management between ArrayExpress (overall study metadata, protocol information, detailed information on biological samples, processed gene expression matrices) and ENA (raw read data) was a good way forward.

As a result of this work, an ArrayExpress **broker account** in ENA was created. The data transformation between MAGE-TAB, the tab-delimited gene expression data format, and the relevant parts of ENA XML were specified and implemented. Processes to synchronize data

release in ArrayExpress and ENA were put in place, so that updates in ArrayExpress would be propagated to ENA in an automated way.

Advantages associated with this approach:

- Single entry point for submitters - Data submitters need to work with only one data submission system, i.e., tools, curation processes, support team.
- Avoid duplication of infrastructure - Raw read data ends up in ENA which is well equipped for working with this data type by providing format transformations, the necessary storage and compute infrastructure. ArrayExpress did not need to replicate this work.
- Datasets are annotated for better usability, and the community benefits from the experience with MIAME/MINSEQE guidelines in ArrayExpress.

Disadvantages:

- Discrepancy in release policies - Different repositories have different policies
 - In ArrayExpress it is possible to hide an already released record if the submitter realised that mistakes were made, or had another good reason.
 - ENA policies allow record suppression, i.e., removal for search indices, but the record remains publicly available if its accession number is known.
- Different technical capabilities
 - ArrayExpress always supported access to private data for editors or reviewers - the data owners had capabilities to give out access details.
 - ENA does not provide this functionality, which often results in entries remaining inaccessible and creates confusion for submitters working through ArrayExpress.
- More difficult technical maintenance, due to the interfaces between the resources. This contributed to the discontinuation of ArrayExpress as a separate resource and its merge within the BioStudies database³².

From MGnify to ENA

A submission to MGnify starts with data producers making a submission to the ENA³³. Through the MGnify portal, users can request analyses of their own or publicly available metagenomic datasets in ENA by providing the corresponding ENA accession numbers. This allows MGnify to access the user's ENA data and metadata and carry out the analysis on their behalf. The resulting outputs are stored in the MGnify system with MGnify accessions, as well as being submitted back to the user's project in ENA.

³² A long-standing ELIXIR Core Data Resource, though now discontinued as a stand-alone resource and exists as a data collection in BioStudies (10.1093/nar/gkaa1062).

³³ <https://docs.mgnify.org/src/docs/dataflow.html>

From EVA to ENA

The EVA data submission workflow begins with submitters providing structured metadata and data files directly to EVA. EVA then **brokers** these to BioSamples and ENA, and subsequently retrieves the relevant metadata and present variant-specific information on the EVA portal, enhancing searchability and findability. In addition, EVA brokers all submitted data to NCBI resources, including dbSNP and dbVar.

Between BioSamples and ENA

The ENA-BioSamples relationship is often misunderstood to be data brokering between repositories, when in fact it is a close relationship based on shared infrastructure. ENA does not 'push' data into BioSamples nor the other way around. Instead (as of 2025), ENA transferred over the management of its sample data (i.e. validation, storage, etc.) to the BioSamples infrastructure. This means that, regardless of which archive a sample record is created in, it is written in the back-end of the BioSamples database. Both BioSamples and ENA pull data from here for public presentation.

This integration not only has significant operational benefits for ENA, but also improves the metadata quality and interoperability between the two archives.

ProteomeXchange Consortium

In the ProteomeXchange (PX) consortium³⁴ metadata exchange is implemented via a centralized brokering approach. When a dataset is submitted to a member repository such as PRIDE, MassIVE, or jPOST, the repository retains the authoritative copy of all raw data and full metadata. A subset of metadata—including the PX identifier, dataset title, submitter information, and sample descriptions—is transmitted (or **brokered**) to ProteomeCentral, the consortium's discovery hub. This partial metadata enables centralized search and cross-referencing across PX members without duplicating the underlying data. Updates to the dataset can be reflected in ProteomeCentral, but PX does not maintain full synchronization of metadata between repositories; the original repository remains the primary source of truth. This model ensures discoverability while minimizing unnecessary data duplication.

The International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (INSDC)

The INSDC operates with a different model - that of **mirroring**.

The INSDC is a partnership between NCBI, EMBL-EBI, and DDBJ databases that has provided global access to nucleotide sequence data for over 40 years. As opposed to the centralized brokering model described above, the INSDC *mirrors* all data and metadata daily across each

³⁴ <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkac1040>

site, through XML dumps and data file transfers to FTP directories. This means that each site has the full complement of data submitted to INSDC.

Mirroring is different to data brokering. It involves both pushing and pulling of data, while data brokering involves only pushing. INSDC's mirroring system helps ensure resilience and reliability of data while supporting rapid data retrieval for users across the globe.

Current Landscape of Multi-omics Submission Support in Deposition Databases

Documentation

Across the selected ELIXIR deposition databases, explicit support for multi-omics data submission is quite limited (Table 3). Only BioImage Archive currently provides user-facing documentation for multi-omics submissions, specifically in the context of spatial-omics.³⁵

For BioSamples and MetaboLights, instructions on how to navigate deposition of such data are referenced in external documentation, (e.g. from MGnify³⁶) as opposed to being highlighted on their own archive's web pages. Interestingly, despite some repositories being inherently 'multi-omic' due to their ability to accept any type of data (and e.g., multiple data files), such as BioStudies and Zenodo, explicit submissions guidance for this data is still lacking. ENA and EGA maintain internal guidance for cross-repository submissions and are the only databases currently developing public-facing documentation (through various initiatives such as the FECA Connect project and ReCODID).

Overall, there appears to be no agreed consensus on how to handle cross-repository submissions across the specific ELIXIR and non-ELIXIR databases above. Recommendations for repository improvements (both technical and non-technical) will be made and formalised as part of Activity 2 of the ELIXIR Data Platform WP2, in 2025/2026.

Database	Multi-omics support / documentation	Notes / URLs
ArrayExpress	None – no documentation or mention	Brokers to ENA & BioStudies
BioImage Archive	Support for spatial omics data & data linking instructions	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/bioimage-archive/help-link/ ; https://www.ebi.ac.uk/bioimage-archive/help-images-at-ebi/
BioSamples	No formal documentation; referenced	https://docs.mgnify.org/src/docs/

³⁵ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/bioimage-archive/help-link/>

³⁶ https://docs.mgnify.org/src/docs/multiomics_submission.html

	by MGnify	multiomics_submission.html
BioStudies	Accepts multiple data types and mentions multi-omics studies	See: BioStudies/ArrayExpress site
EGA	Internal SOPs; developing public guidance ongoing	FEGA Connect project
EMDB	None – no documentation or mention	N/A
EMPIAR	None – no documentation or mention	N/A
ENA	None – no documentation or mention	N/A
MetaboLights	No documentation; referenced by MGnify	https://docs.mgnify.org/src/docs/multiomics_submission.html
PDB	None – no documentation or mention	N/A
PRIDE	None – no documentation or mention	N/A
Zenodo	Accepts any data types in one submission	https://about.zenodo.org/

Table 3. Deposition databases and support for multi-omics

Data linking

Conceptually, there could be three approaches to multi-omics submission using datatype-specific repositories (Figure 2): (1) single-entry submission, where all omics datasets are submitted together in a single study record through one entry point but stored and displayed in the relevant specialized repositories³⁷; (2) coordinated sequential submission, in which datasets are submitted to different repositories stepwise, with one step dependent on the previous to generate identifiers for optimal linking; and (3) flexible multi-step submission, in which datasets can be submitted to repositories independently, and simply linked retrospectively via shared identifiers. As highlighted above, data linking is a necessary step in all approaches to facilitate effective discoverability and re-use.

We evaluated each repository's technical capacity to integrate and link multiple data types. To do this we investigated support for potential linking mechanisms that are common points of convergence for research data - namely Pubmed IDs, DOIs, ORCIDs, BioSample accession numbers, and others.

Our landscape analysis indicates that out of all the repositories consulted, cross-references are supported by all ELIXIR and non-ELIXIR resources as a minimum, though this appears to be only at the overarching dataset level. All resources also support assigning Pubmed IDs and

³⁷ <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC6323949/>

ORCIDs to records, however to pose as a useful linking mechanism this would need to be indexed by all archives, which is currently not the case.

All archives support linking BioSample accessions to records, enabling a more granular, sample-level linking. Multi-omics projects involving EBI such as HoloFood³⁸ and ReCoDID³⁹ have already applied this strategy. In the case of EGA, the private status of BioSamples can be addressed by creating a public proxy sample in BioSamples for linking purposes. However, sample-level linking could be further improved in repositories such as EGA and MetaboLights by ensuring that linked samples are fully searchable.

Figure 2. Three proposed conceptual multi-omics submission approaches. a) Single-entry indicates a comprehensive submission using one entry point. b) Co-ordinated sequential indicates multiple entry points for different elements of the submission in a required order. c) Flexible multi-step indicates multiple entry points but no required submission order; links are added retrospectively.

Outcomes and expected impact

Data sharing in life sciences has evolved over decades—over 50 years in the case of protein structures—through diverse policies and repository practices. This fragmented landscape creates challenges for researchers managing larger, more complex datasets while meeting FAIR data-sharing mandates from funders and publishers. WP2 addresses these challenges by strengthening connections between ELIXIR Nodes generating data and the resources

³⁸ <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC11724189/>

³⁹ <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC11835595/>

publishing it. The landscape analysis presented here underpins the definition of best practices for data brokering and their implementation in pilot tools.

The review of repository role management reveals a lack of standardisation. While the submitter–author distinction is common, inconsistent terminology and reliance on free text hinder interoperability and automation. The roles of submitter and broker are conceptually different, yet repository support rarely reflects this, with a single helpdesk often covering both. Wider use of controlled vocabularies and clearer role differentiation would mainly improve interoperability and raise recognition of professionals supporting data producers (data stewards). For 3rd party tools used in submissions, introducing traceability features to record which tool was used would allow providers to demonstrate impact and uptake within communities.

Analysis of data flows between repositories highlights the complexity of standardising submission workflows. Current terminology does not always distinguish between brokering, metadata harvesting, and data sharing. In this context, defining brokering as a repository submitting information to another repository on behalf of the original data producer might offer a clearer framework. Greater clarity around these workflows would enhance understanding among both researchers and support teams, strengthening the ecosystem.

The overview of multi-omics submissions shows that repository support remains fragmented. While some guidance exists, most linking across datasets relies on accession numbers or publication IDs which submitters should usually provide manually. This creates risks of missing links and places additional burden on researchers. With multi-omics and spatial-omics becoming central to life sciences, harmonised repository support and centralised information are urgently needed. Aligning technical development would simplify submissions, ensure interoperability, and maximise reuse of complex datasets. Ongoing efforts such as the MARS initiative⁴⁰ are providing proof of concept for a standardised, interoperable framework for multi-omics submissions. This coordinated sequential flow begins with registering samples in BioSamples so identifiers can be reused across repositories, ensuring fine-grained connections across datasets.

Overall, the findings highlight opportunities to reduce researcher burden, improve workflows, and enhance interoperability. By adopting clearer role definitions, supporting brokering tools, and harmonising multi-omics submissions, repositories can enable more efficient, FAIR-aligned data sharing that accelerates discovery.

⁴⁰ <https://github.com/elixir-europe/MARS>

Dissemination Plans

Upload to Zenodo within the ELIXIR Zenodo Community⁴¹.

⁴¹ <https://zenodo.org/communities/elixir>